

Extended Data File 5: Full text records sought for retrieval and assessed for eligibility

Article	Include	Review Article	Quantitative Data only	Diverse settings	Mixed Pops	Role of GP not detailed	Full text not available	Rated 1 or 2 for Richness
Amos, T. B., et al. (2015). "Inappropriate prescribing in a large community-dwelling older population: a focus on prevalence and how it relates to patient and physician characteristics." <i>40</i> (1): 7-13.	Y							X
Anderson, K., et al. (2014). "Prescriber barriers and enablers to minimising potentially inappropriate medications in adults: a systematic review and thematic synthesis." <i>4</i> (12): e006544.	N	X						
Anderson, K., et al. (2020). "GP-Led Deprescribing in Community-Living Older Australians: An Exploratory Controlled Trial." <i>Journal of the American Geriatrics Society</i> <i>68</i> (2): 403-410.	Y							
Beuscart, J.-B., et al. (2017). "A systematic review of the outcomes reported in trials of medication review in older patients: the need for a core outcome set." <i>British journal of clinical pharmacology</i> <i>83</i> (5): 942-952.	N	X						
Bigi, C. and G. Bocci (2017). "The key role of clinical and community health nurses in pharmacovigilance." <i>73</i> (11): 1379-1387.	N	X						
Boparai, M. K. and B. Korc-Grodzicki (2011). "Prescribing for older adults." <i>The Mount Sinai journal of medicine, New York</i> <i>78</i> (4): 613-626.	N						X	
Bregnhøj, L., et al. "Combined intervention programme reduces inappropriate prescribing in elderly patients exposed to polypharmacy in primary care." <i>65</i> (2): 199-207.	Y							X
Campins, L., et al. (2017). "Randomized controlled trial of an intervention to improve drug appropriateness in community-dwelling polymedicated elderly people." <i>34</i> (1): 36-42.	N		X					

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Cantrill, J. A., et al. (2011). "Qualitative insights into general practitioners' views on the appropriateness of their long-term prescribing." <i>International Journal of Pharmacy Practice</i> 8 (1): 20-26.	Y							
Chen, Z. and A. Buonanno (2017). "Geriatric Polypharmacy: Two Physicians' Personal Perspectives." 33 (2): 283-288.	Y							
Chiang-Hanisko, L., et al. (2015). "Medication Use Among Ethnically Diverse Older Adults in the United States." <i>RESEARCH IN GERONTOLOGICAL NURSING</i> 8 (6): 273-285.	N		X			X		
Clyne, B., et al. (2013). "Addressing potentially inappropriate prescribing in older patients: development and pilot study of an intervention in primary care (the OPTI-SCRIPT study)." 13 (1): 307.	Y							
Clyne, B., et al. (2015). "Effectiveness of a Multifaceted Intervention for Potentially Inappropriate Prescribing in Older Patients in Primary Care: A Cluster-Randomized Controlled Trial (OPTI-SCRIPT Study)." <i>Annals of family medicine</i> 13 (6): 545-553.	Y N							X
Clyne, B., et al. (2016). "Potentially inappropriate or specifically appropriate? Qualitative evaluation of general practitioners views on prescribing, polypharmacy and potentially inappropriate prescribing in older people." <i>BMC family practice</i> 17 (1): 109-109.	Y							
Clyne, B., et al. (2016). "A process evaluation of a cluster randomised trial to reduce potentially inappropriate prescribing in older people in primary care (OPTI-SCRIPT study)." <i>Trials</i> 17 (1): 386-386.	Y							
Clyne, B., et al. (2016). "Interventions to Address Potentially Inappropriate Prescribing in Community-Dwelling Older Adults: A Systematic Review of Randomized Controlled Trials." <i>Journal of the American Geriatrics Society</i> 64 (6): 1210-1222.	N	X						
Clyne, B., et al. (2016). "Sustained effectiveness of a multifaceted intervention to reduce potentially inappropriate prescribing in older patients in primary care (OPTI-SCRIPT study)." <i>Implementation science : IS</i> 11 (1): 79-79.	Y N							X

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Clyne, B., et al. (2017). "Beliefs about prescribed medication among older patients with polypharmacy: a mixed methods study in primary care." <u>The British journal of general practice : the journal of the Royal College of General Practitioners</u> 67 (660): e507-e518.	Y							
Cooper, J. A., et al. (2015). "Interventions to improve the appropriate use of polypharmacy in older people: a Cochrane systematic review." <u>BMJ open</u> 5 (12): e009235.	N	X						
Cossette, B., et al. (2019). "A pharmacist-physician intervention model using a computerized alert system to reduce high-risk medication use in primary care." 75 (7): 1017-1023.	Y N							X
Cross, A. J., et al. "Deprescribing potentially inappropriate medications in memory clinic patients (DePIMM): A feasibility study." 16 (10): 1392-1397.	N		X					
Cullinan, S., et al. "A meta-synthesis of potentially inappropriate prescribing in older patients." 31 (8): 631-638.	N	X						
Davies, E. A. and M. S. O'Mahony (2015). "Adverse drug reactions in special populations - the elderly." 80 (4): 796-807.	N	X						
Davies, L. E., et al. (2020). "Adverse Outcomes of Polypharmacy in Older People: Systematic Review of Reviews." <u>Journal of the American Medical Directors Association</u> 21 (2): 181-187.	N	X						
Doherty, A. J., et al. "Barriers and facilitators to deprescribing in primary care: a systematic review." 4 (3).	N	X						
Doucette, W. R., et al. "Initial development of the Systems Approach to Home Medication Management (SAHMM) model." 13 (1): 39-47.	N				X			

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Foubert, K., et al. (2020). "Pharmacist-led medication review in community-dwelling older patients using the GheOP3S-tool: General practitioners' acceptance and implementation of pharmacists' recommendations." <u>Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice</u> 26 (3): 962-972.	YN							X
Fried, T. R., et al. "Primary care clinicians' experiences with treatment decision making for older persons with multiple conditions." 171 (1): 75-80.	Y							
Geurts, M. M. E., et al. (2016). "Implications of a clinical medication review and a pharmaceutical care plan of polypharmacy patients with a cardiovascular disorder." 38 (4): 808-815.	Y							
Godfrey, C. M., et al. (2013). "Homecare safety and medication management with older adults: a scoping review of the quantitative and qualitative evidence." <u>JBI Database of Systematic Reviews & Implementation Reports</u> 11 (7): 82-130.	N						X	
Halli-Tierney, A. D., et al. "Polypharmacy: Evaluating Risks and Deprescribing." 100 (1): 32-38.	Y							
Hazen, A. C. M., et al. (2019). "Non-dispensing pharmacists' actions and solutions of drug therapy problems among elderly polypharmacy patients in primary care." 36 (5): 544-551.	N					X		
Heser, K., et al. (2018). "Perspective of elderly patients on chronic use of potentially inappropriate medication - Results of the qualitative CIM-TRIAD study." 13 (9): e0202068.	Y							
Hilmer, S. N. and D. Gnjidic (2018). "Deprescribing: the emerging evidence for and the practice of the 'geriatrician's salute'." 47 (5): 638-640.	N					X		
Hofer-Düeckelmann, C. (2012). "Gender and polypharmacotherapy in the elderly: A clinical challenge." <u>Handbook of experimental pharmacology</u> 214 ((Hofer-Düeckelmann C., c.dueckelmann@salk.at) Pharmacy Department, Landesapotheke am St. Johannis Spital, Salzburg, Austria): 169-182.	N					X		

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Hoisnard, L., et al. "Do older adults know the purpose of their medications? A survey among community-dwelling people." <i>75(2)</i> : 255-263.	Y							
Holmes, H. M. and A. Todd (2017). "The Role of Patient Preferences in Deprescribing." <i>33(2)</i> : 165-175.	N			X		X		
Hughes, L. D., et al. "Guidelines for people not for diseases: the challenges of applying UK clinical guidelines to people with multimorbidity." <i>42(1)</i> : 62-69.	Y							
Jäger, C., et al. (2017). "Impact of a tailored program on the implementation of evidence-based recommendations for multimorbid patients with polypharmacy in primary care practices—results of a cluster-randomized controlled trial." <i>Implementation science : IS 12(1)</i> : 8-8.	Y							
Kaufman, G. (2016). "Identifying polypharmacy in the primary care setting." <i>Practice Nursing 27(1)</i> : 28-33.	N						X	
Khalil, H. (2011). "Prescribing for the elderly: ethical considerations." <i>Australian journal of primary health 17(1)</i> : 2-3.	N						X	
Khalil, H., et al. (2017). "Professional, structural and organisational interventions in primary care for reducing medication errors." <i>Cochrane Database Syst Rev 10(10)</i> : Cd003942.	N	X						
Koberlein, J., et al. (2013). "General practitioners' views on polypharmacy and its consequences for patient health care." <i>14</i> : 119.	Y							
Kratz, T. and A. Diefenbacher (2019). "Psychopharmacological Treatment in Older People: Avoiding Drug Interactions and Polypharmacy." <i>Deutsches Arzteblatt international 116(29-30)</i> : 508-518.	N	X						

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Krishnaswami, A., et al. (2019). "Deprescribing in Older Adults With Cardiovascular Disease." 73(20): 2584-2595.	N	X						
Maidment, I. D., et al. (2020). "Medication management in older people: the MEMORABLE realist synthesis." 8: 26.	N	X						
Maidment, I., et al. (2017). "Developing a framework for a novel multi-disciplinary, multi-agency intervention(s), to improve medication management in community-dwelling older people on complex medication regimens (MEMORABLE)--a realist synthesis." Systematic Reviews 6(1): 125.	N	X						
Maidment, I., et al. (2020). "Towards an understanding of the burdens of medication management affecting older people: the MEMORABLE realist synthesis." 20(1): 1-17.	N	X						
Mallet, L., et al. (2007). "The challenge of managing drug interactions in elderly people." 370: 185-191.	Y							
Mantelli, S., et al. (2018). "How general practitioners would deprescribe in frail oldest-old with polypharmacy - the LESS study." BMC family practice 19(1): 169-169.	Y N							X
Nair, N. P., et al. (2016). "Hospitalization in older patients due to adverse drug reactions - the need for a prediction tool." CLINICAL INTERVENTIONS IN AGING 11: 497-505.	N	X						
Ostini, R., et al. "Knowing how to stop: ceasing prescribing when the medicine is no longer required." 18(1): 68-72.	N	X						
Parker, M., et al. (2015). "GPs, medications and older people: A qualitative study of general practitioners' approaches to potentially inappropriate medications in older people." 34(2): 134-139.	Y							

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Patsuree, A., et al. (2016). "Experiences relating to adverse drug reactions in the community: a cross-sectional survey among patients and the general public in Thailand." <u>Expert opinion on drug safety</u> 15 (3): 287-295.	Y							
Patterson, S. M., et al. (2012). "Interventions to improve the appropriate use of polypharmacy for older people." <u>Cochrane Database Syst Rev</u> (5): Cd008165.	N	X						
Peterson, G. M., et al. (2018). "Practice pharmacists and the opportunity to support general practitioners in deprescribing in the older person." <u>Journal of Pharmacy Practice & Research</u> 48 (2): 183-185.	Y							
Pindolia, V. K., et al. "Mitigation of medication mishaps via medication therapy management." 43 (4): 611-620.	N					X		
Pohontsch, N. J., et al. (2017). "General practitioners' views on (long-term) prescription and use of problematic and potentially inappropriate medication for oldest-old patients-A qualitative interview study with GPs (CIM-TRIAD study)." 18 (1): 22.	Y							
Ponticelli, C., et al. (2015). "Drug management in the elderly adult with chronic kidney disease: a review for the primary care physician." <u>Mayo Clinic Proceedings</u> 90 (5): 633-645.	N	X						
Reed, R. L., et al. (2015). "Why do older people with multi-morbidity experience unplanned hospital admissions from the community: a root cause analysis." <u>BMC Health Services Research</u> 15 .	Y							
Ridge, A., et al. (2019). "Assessing risk of adverse drug reactions in the elderly: a feasibility study." 41 (6): 1483-1490.	Y							
Riker, G. I. and S. M. Setter (2013). "Polypharmacy in older adults at home: what it is and what to do about it-implications for home healthcare and hospice, part 2." <u>Home Healthcare Nurse</u> 31 (2): 65-77.	N					X		

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Rogers, S., et al. (2014). "Medicines management support to older people: understanding the context of systems failure." <i>4</i> (7): e005302.	Y							
Rozsnyai, Z., et al. (2020). "What do older adults with multimorbidity and polypharmacy think about deprescribing? The LESS study - a primary care-based survey." <i>BMC geriatrics</i> 20 (1): 1-11.	Y							
Schuling, J., et al. (2012). "Deprescribing medication in very elderly patients with multimorbidity: the view of Dutch GPs. A qualitative study." <i>BMC family practice</i> 13 (1): 56-62.	Y							
Shade, M. Y., et al. (2014). "Potentially Inappropriate Medications in Community-Dwelling Older Adults." <i>RESEARCH IN GERONTOLOGICAL NURSING</i> 7 (4): 178-192.	N							
Sinnott, C., et al. (2017). "Improving medication management for patients with multimorbidity in primary care: a qualitative feasibility study of the MY COMRADE implementation intervention." <i>Pilot and Feasibility Studies</i> 3 (1): 14.	Y							
Skinner, M. (2015). "A literature review: polypharmacy protocol for primary care." 36 (5): 367-371.e364.	N	X						
Sloeserwij, V. M., et al. (2019). "Effects of non-dispensing pharmacists integrated in general practice on medication-related hospitalisations." <i>British journal of clinical pharmacology</i> 85 (10): 2321-2331.	N					X		
Spinewine, A., et al. "Appropriate prescribing in elderly people: how well can it be measured and optimised?" 370 (9582): 173-184.	N	X						
Stevenson, F. A., et al. "A systematic review of the research on communication between patients and health care professionals about medicines: the consequences for concordance." 7 (3): 235-245.	N	X						

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Stewart, D., et al. (2017). "Guidance to manage inappropriate polypharmacy in older people: systematic review and future developments." <i>Expert opinion on drug safety</i> 16 (2): 203-213.	N	X						
Tecklenborg, S., et al. (2020). "Interventions to Reduce Adverse Drug Event-Related Outcomes in Older Adults: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis." 37 (2): 91-98.	N	X						
Tinetti, M. E., et al. "Potential pitfalls of disease-specific guidelines for patients with multiple conditions." 351 (27): 2870-2874.	Y N							X
Topinkova, E., et al. (2012). "Evidence-based strategies for the optimization of pharmacotherapy in older people." 29 (6): 477-494.	N	X						
Touchette, D. R., et al. (2012). "Safety-focused medication therapy management: a randomized controlled trial." <i>Journal of the American Pharmacists Association: JAPhA</i> 52 (5): 603-612.	N		X			X		
Ulley, J., et al. "Deprescribing interventions and their impact on medication adherence in community-dwelling older adults with polypharmacy: a systematic review." 19 .	N	X						
Vrdoljak, D. and J. A. Borovac (2015). "Medication in the elderly - considerations and therapy prescription guidelines." 44 (2): 159-168.	N	X						
Wallace, E., et al. (2015). "Managing patients with multimorbidity in primary care." 350 : h176.	Y							
Yap, A. F., et al. (2016). "Medication adherence in the elderly." 7 (2): 64-67.	N					X		